

IDIOMS AND PHRASES IN ENGLISH

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Annotation. Every language has its own idioms and expressions, and there are many useful phrases to learn in English. Idioms are words or phrases that are not taken literally and usually have a cultural meaning behind them. Maybe you've heard some of them, especially in TV shows and movies, and you've wondered why you can't understand these idioms even though you totally understand the words.

Key words: idioms, phrases, adjective, noun, verb, expression, context, equivalent, meaning

Learning English idioms and phrases can take some time, but some are more popular than others and it helps if you know them. When you learn English phrases and expressions, you will feel more confident, especially when speaking with native English speakers. If you don't understand idioms, you can't understand context. That's why we've collected the most common English phrases and expressions, so you can understand their true meaning.

An idiom is a phrase that conveys an indirect meaning, usually attached to a phrase but some idioms become idioms while retaining the literal meaning of the idiom. The figurative meaning of an idiom belonging to the group of formulaic languages differs from its literal meaning. Idioms and phrases play an important role in the richness of language. If we want to make our sentences more effective, idioms and phrases can be the most useful resource.

An idiom is a group of words, phrases, or expressions that have a symbolic rather than a literal meaning in common usage. It is a form of artistic expression specific to a movement, period, individual, medium or instrument. An idiom is a

phrase or expression used in everyday English to express certain ideas or thoughts. Understanding English idioms is important because they require a deeper understanding of the English language to understand what someone means when they use them in a conversation. Idioms may seem complicated at first, but learning them can be a lot of fun. If you're interested in improving your English, read on to find out why idioms are important to your English learning. Idioms give you a new way to express yourself in English

The meaning of an idiom usually depends on the context in which it is used. In America, when someone tells you to "break your leg", they don't mean it literally, but usually wish them luck before the show. Likewise, if someone asks you to "think outside the box," it means you need to take a different approach than usual. Its symbolic meaning is different from the definition or literal meaning of the words that make it up. Idioms express a figurative meaning that is difficult to understand only by interpreting the words literally. For example, "beyond the pale" means that something is "out of line" or wrong. You can only know this by understanding the meaning of the phrase based on context or by having someone explain it to you.

There are different idioms and people use them in all languages. It can be difficult to translate them into other languages, as some meanings may be lost. Nevertheless, there are equivalents that fill the gaps between languages. English has an infinite number of idiomatic expressions.

1. The best of both worlds – means you can enjoy two different opportunities at the same time.

"By working part-time and looking after her kids two days a week she managed to get the best of both worlds."

2. 'Speak of the devil' – this means that the person you're just talking about actually appears at that moment.

"Hi Tom, speak of the devil, I was just telling Sara about your new car."

3. 'See eye to eye' – this means agreeing with someone.

“They finally saw eye to eye on the business deal.”

4. ‘Once in a blue moon’ – an event that happens infrequently.

“I only go to the cinema once in a blue moon.”

5. ‘When pigs fly’ – something that will never happen.

“When pigs fly she’ll tidy up her room.”

Phrases

A phrase is a group of small words that express an idea but are not a complete sentence. You use phrases in your writing and speaking every day. There are many types of idioms, some of which play a technical role in your writing, while others play a descriptive role. Whatever role a phrase plays, it serves one simple purpose: to enrich your sentences by giving your words context, detail, and clarity.

Verb phrase

A verb phrase (VP, also called a "verb group") consists of a main verb and its auxiliary verbs (including modals), for example:

We work from 9 o'clock.

I'm going to France next week.

It may be under repair.

Adjective clause

An adjective phrase can be a single adjective or a group of words built around an adjective, for example:

He has smart ideas.

It was a huge meal.

The students were very bored with the movie.

Additional phrase

An adverbial phrase can be a group of words built around a single adverb or a single adverb, for example:

Please do it now.

He spoke very softly.

They did it as fast as they could.

Prepositional phrase

An introductory word is followed by its subject (usually a noun phrase), for example:

They argued about money.

The window was behind a large brown couch.

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